

**ANALYSIS OF CONCEPTS AND THEORIES REGARDING
RACE AND TESOL**

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Race and TESOL (Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages) intersect in various ways, shaping the experiences of both teachers and learners in language classrooms. In this context, race refers to a social construct that categorizes people based on physical characteristics such as skin colour, hair texture, and facial features. TESOL, on the other hand, is a field of education that focuses on teaching English to individuals who have a different native language. When examining race and TESOL, it is important to consider the following concepts and theories:

Culture and Identity: Race intersects with culture and identity, as individuals from different racial backgrounds often bring diverse cultural perspectives and experiences to the language classroom. Teachers need to be aware of these variations and create an inclusive learning environment that values and respects different cultural identities.

Linguicism and Language Hierarchy: Linguicism refers to discrimination or prejudice based on a person's language or linguistic background. Within TESOL, language hierarchy can exist, where certain varieties of English are considered superior to others. This can lead to biases against learners who speak English as a second or additional language, particularly those from non-English dominant racial backgrounds. Teachers should challenge linguistic prejudices and promote linguistic diversity in the classroom.

Critical Race Theory (CRT): CRT is a theoretical framework that examines how race intersects with power, privilege, and oppression. In the context of TESOL, CRT can be used to analyze systemic inequalities and biases that affect language learners and teachers. It emphasizes the need to critically examine educational practices, policies, and curricula to address racial inequities and foster social justice in TESOL classrooms.

White Privilege and Centering Whiteness: TESOL has historically been influenced by native speaker norms and centered on white, Western standards of English. This can perpetuate white privilege and marginalize learners from racial and linguistic minority backgrounds. Teachers should be aware of these dynamics and strive to challenge the centrality of whiteness in language

teaching, adopting inclusive pedagogies that validate diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Anti-Racist Pedagogy: Anti-racist pedagogy involves actively challenging and dismantling racist practices and structures in education. In TESOL, anti-racist pedagogy calls for promoting social justice, equity, and inclusion in language classrooms. It involves critically examining curriculum materials, promoting culturally responsive teaching, and creating opportunities for learners to explore issues of race, identity, and social justice in English language learning. By understanding and applying these concepts and theories, TESOL practitioners can work towards creating inclusive and equitable language learning environments that recognize and value the diverse racial backgrounds and identities of learners.

Being specific, the article explores core concepts and theories, which provide with specific information and researches about “race, ethnicity, culture, racialization, racism, critical race theory and critical white studies” (Kubota & Lin 2006, p.471). As the ideas related to race, racism, racialization are familiar topics to all people around the world, however they can be referred differently in various contexts. Whereas, there are several social categories such as race, racialization and racism, which have already been started to be investigated by TESOL and Second language teaching because race can be considered as a crucial issue in term of teaching English around the world. Although the term “*race*” has been defined by many scholars, it can be seen as a relative term than absolute including classification of people according to genes or biological features. As we cannot differentiate people in terms of biological evidences only, however race can be defined as a classifying people according to social and biological features concerning discourse that our beliefs were based on.

On the other hand, the term “race” can be compared parallel to “imagined community” (Anderson, 1983). That means the term “race” is imagined as community that how we imagine and perceive that another race is beyond the boundary (Miles, 1987). Not only ‘race’, but also ‘ethnicity’ and ‘culture’ are terms to differentiate human being according to perceived social features can be basis for “racialization” and “racism”. As it is mentioned above that “racialization” is separating people based on process that are related to biological factors which categorize people into separate racial groups. Furthermore, racialization can create social groups related to biological features, however it is not stable that racial significations are not always constant. The term “racism” sometimes can be seen similar to racialization, yet we cannot

define racism as a simple term because there are many definitions but it can be simply defined as discrimination or prejudice, which is directed some people whose race is differ from others who argue that their race is superior.

Overall, the terms “race”, “racialization”, “racism” are very important factors in terms of shaping social , cultural features of language teaching and learning because every teacher should take into consideration that race is closely connected to the term “culture” in terms of conducting lesson whereas every teacher or learner should have equal rights.

References:

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